

THE ROLE OF TEACHING PROVERBS AND SAYINGS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING CLASSES AT SCHOOLS

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Abstract: Our article is based on one of the effective principles of work on the development of speech skills and abilities is to familiarize schoolchildren with the proverbs of the language being studied. Proverbs allow students to get in touch with the culture of the country of the language being studied. They convince students that the same thoughts and aspirations are characteristic of different peoples to serve their moral education. Familiarity with proverbs evokes positive emotions in schoolchildren, which significantly affects the motivation for using a foreign language as a means of intercultural communication.

Proverbs and sayings play a huge role in teaching a foreign language. It is necessary to develop a linguistic flair in the child's thinking, which helps him to select linguistic means for figurative utterance. Scientists highly appreciate the importance of fiction and oral folk art. According to O.I. Paley proverbs and sayings give an opportunity to penetrate into another system of thinking, to get acquainted with another system of values. The deep content of proverbs and sayings not only develops students' thinking, but also has an educational effect.²⁴ The methodological and practical value of using proverbs and sayings in the process of teaching the foreign language is very great. A huge variety of proverbs provides an opportunity to use them in working with students of any age. The deep content of these short statements not only develops students' thinking, but also has great educational value.

Teaching proverbs and sayings at English lessons allows you to solve a number of didactic tasks, namely:

Teaching: improving pronunciation and pronunciation skills, activating grammatical skills, developing translation skills, enriching vocabulary of students.

Developing: broadening their horizons, developing skills to express their thoughts in a foreign language, activating thinking abilities.

Educational: formation of moral and ethical principles, fostering a tolerant attitude towards the culture and traditions of other people.

²⁴ Paley O.I. Work with proverbs and sayings at the English lesson in IX grade. // Foreign languages at school, 2000. № 1. P. 40–42.

Motivating: developing interest in learning a foreign language through reading the original language, forming and increasing sustainable motivation, developing cognitive abilities of students.

Native English speakers often use proverbs and sayings in everyday conversation, sometimes without even realizing it. Sayings can tell you more about the culture of the country whose language you are studying than any textbook. Such sayings clearly demonstrate which things or phenomena play a big role for a particular nation, and also help to understand what is considered good form and what is bad. In English, with a higher activity in phraseology than in Russian, the following integral meanings prevail: caution, diligence, restraint in speech:

«It is ill to waken sleeping dogs. Let sleeping dogs lie" (Do not wake sleeping dogs. Don't wake up famously while it's quiet);

"Put not your hand between the bark and the tree" (Don't put your hands between the bark and the tree. Their dogs are biting — someone else's do not poke).

Anglo-Saxon culture is characterized by a disapproving attitude to the unrestrained verbal flow of feelings:

"Pigs grunt about everything and nothing" (There is a reason, there is no reason — the pig grunts anyway. You can't put a handkerchief on someone else's mouth. Boneless tongue: what he wants, he babbles);

"First think, then speak" (Think first, then speak).

In order to have the correct translation of proverbs and sayings for schoolchildren into their native language, let's consider four main ways of translating figurative phraseology, which are distinguished by V. N. Komissarov, L. F. Dmitrieva, S. E. Kuntsevich, E. A. Martinkevich, N. F. Smirnova.²⁵ 1. Phraseological equivalent. The entire set of values of the translated combination is saved.

For example:

All in good time – Все в свое время

To play with fire - Играть с огнем

Appetite comes with eating- Аппетит приходит во время еды

The use of such an equivalent helps to accurately reproduce a foreign phraseology, but there are relatively few phraseological equivalents.

2. Phraseological analogue. In this method, a Russian phraseology is used, similar in meaning to English, but based on a different image.

For example:

Work one's fingers to the bone- Работать не покладая рук .

Make hay while the sun shines- Куй железо пока горячо .

²⁵ Dmitrieva L. F., Kuntsevich S.E., Martinkevich E. A., Smirnova N. F. English - Translation course. A book for students from Moscow- Rostov-on-Don.

When in Rome, do as Romans do- В чужой монастырь со своим уставом не ходят.

3. Calculus. A method such as calculus or word-by-word translation is also used, although such a method is not always acceptable. L.F. Dmitrieva notes that this method can be used only when an expression is obtained, the imagery of which is easily perceived by a native speaker of the translated language.

For example:

Time is a great healer- Время великий лекарь

Time flies- Время летит

Keep a dog and bark yourself- Держать собаку, а лаять самому

If there are no phraseological units equivalent to the original phraseological unit in the language into which the translation is carried out, then it is necessary to look for one-word partial equivalents of phraseological units corresponding in meaning and coloring of the word.

4. Descriptive translation of phraseological units. This is another method that L. F. Dmitrieva, S. E. Kuntsevich, E. A. Martinkevich, N. F. Smirnova distinguish, it should be used to explain the meaning of proverbs and sayings that have neither an analogue nor an equivalent in the Russian language and are not subject to literal translation.²⁶

It is a good fishing in troubled water-. В мутной воде рыба ловится лучше.

A skeleton in the cupboard – Семейная тайна.

To have butterflies in stomach- Нервничать от страха.

Thus, we can say that the national character is a set of specific physical and spiritual qualities, norms of behavior and activity typical for a representative of a particular nation. Comparison of proverbs and sayings of different nations shows how much these nations have in common, which, in turn, contributes to their better understanding and rapprochement. We agree with A. A. Leontiev's opinion that respect for the national culture, for the native languages of other peoples is impossible without knowledge of this culture, without at least the most general awareness of these languages.²⁷

The use of proverbs and sayings in the practice of teaching English will undoubtedly contribute to the better development of these subjects, expanding knowledge about the language, vocabulary and features of its functioning. On the other hand, their study is an additional source of linguistic and socio-cultural knowledge. The need to find means of equivalent translation of expressions into the native language develops translation skills and abilities. Working with proverbs and

²⁶ Dmitrieva L. F., Kuntsevich S.E., Martinkevich E. A., Smirnova N. F. English - Translation course. A book for students from Moscow- Rostov-on-Don.

²⁷ Leontiev, A. A. Journey on the map of the languages of the world / A. A. Leontiev. — M., 1990

sayings motivates young learners to work with a dictionary. The wide functionality of proverbs and sayings allows you to work out pronunciation, improve rhythmic and intonation skills, activate and automate many grammatical phenomena, enrich the vocabulary of students, help them learn the structure of the language, feel its emotional expressiveness, develop memory and creative initiative. Working on proverbs and sayings, students comprehend the variability of the language, its expressive means and figurative content, perceive and "appropriate" the language, respond creatively, expressing their personal attitude. This is the basis for the formation of not only language competence, but also an aesthetic sense. Work with proverbs and sayings, which can be carried out both in the classroom and in extracurricular work in the form of various tasks, contests, quizzes. The use of proverbs and sayings in foreign language lessons contributes to the better development of this subject, expanding knowledge about the language and the peculiarities of its functioning. Familiarization with the culture of the country of the language being studied through elements of folklore gives students a sense of involvement in the linguistic culture of other people. The research materials allow us to draw the following conclusions – proverbs adorn speech, make it more accurate, expressive, helping to avoid repetitions. Learning proverbs and sayings can make people’s speech colorful and bright. The methodological and practical values of using proverbs and sayings in the process of learning English were revealed. Thus, the use of proverbs and sayings is appropriate for illustrating grammatical phenomena and fixing them in speech. Due to its lexical and grammatical richness, proverbs and sayings can be used to enrich the vocabulary. Also, as an incentive, they can be used for speech development. The study of proverbs and sayings contributes to the enrichment of vocabulary, allows you to develop memory, and also introduces you to folk wisdom.

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